

Learning Competencies of Junior High School Learners in Home Economics in District V, Manila City Division

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Abstract

The development of competent learners in Home Economics (HE) is essential in ensuring effective acquisition of practical skills and technical knowledge aligned with the goals of the K–12 curriculum. This study was conducted to determine the level of learning competencies of Junior High School learners in Home Economics in District V, Division of Manila City, during the School Year 2025–2026. Specifically, it assessed learners' competencies across four strands: Dressmaking, Cookery, Handicraft Making, and Food Processing, as perceived by their teachers and school heads. It also examined the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by HE teachers that may hinder the effective development of learning competencies.

The study employed a descriptive research design, with HE teachers and school heads as respondents. A structured questionnaire served as the primary data-gathering instrument, while the

Average Weighted Mean and t-test were used to analyze the data.

Findings revealed that the level of learning competencies of Junior High School learners was generally moderate across the four strands. Results further showed no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and school heads, indicating a shared understanding of learners' competencies. Moreover, the problems encountered by HE teachers were rated as moderately serious, suggesting challenges that may affect the effective delivery of practical and technical lessons. While learners demonstrate adequate levels of competency in Home Economics, there is a need for targeted instructional interventions, professional support for teachers, and enhanced learning resources. The findings of the study served as the basis for the development of an action plan aimed at strengthening the learning competencies of Junior High School learners in Home Economics.

Keywords: *Home Economics, Learning Competencies, Junior High School Learners, Practical Skills, Action Plan*

INTRODUCTION

Home Economics (HE) plays a vital role in equipping learners with practical skills, technical knowledge, and problem-solving abilities necessary for productivity, employability, and entrepreneurship. Under the K–12 curriculum, HE provides learners with hands-on competencies in various areas, including Dressmaking, Cookery, Handicraft Making, and Food Processing. The effectiveness of this program largely depends on the quality of instruction and the ability of teachers to facilitate competency-based learning experiences.

The Department of Education (DepEd) emphasizes the importance of developing learners' competencies in HE to ensure they acquire skills that are relevant to real-life applications, future

employment, or entrepreneurial opportunities. Learners are expected to demonstrate proficiency in practical tasks, proper use of tools and materials, adherence to safety and hygiene standards, and the ability to plan, produce, and evaluate outputs across different strands of Home Economics.

Despite curriculum support, challenges persist in the delivery of HE instruction. Limited facilities, inadequate teaching materials, insufficient training for teachers, and varying student motivation levels can affect the effective development of learning competencies. Understanding the alignment or differences in perceptions between teachers and school heads regarding learners' competencies is essential for designing instructional interventions and targeted support mechanisms.

In view of these considerations, this study aimed to determine the level of learning competencies of Junior High School learners in Home Economics in District V, Division of Manila City. Specifically, it assessed learners' competencies across the four HE strands, examined differences in perceptions between teachers and school heads, identified problems encountered by teachers, and proposed an action plan to enhance students' competencies. The findings of this study are expected to provide valuable insights for school administrators, curriculum planners, and policymakers in improving the quality of Home Economics instruction.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design to assess the level of learning competencies among Junior High School learners in Home Economics. The design was appropriate for describing existing learner competencies, examining perceptions of teachers and school heads, and identifying challenges encountered in teaching HE without manipulating any variables.

Participants

The participants of the study consisted of a total enumeration of 42 Home Economics teachers and 6 school heads from six public junior high schools in District V, Manila City Division. The respondents were selected due to their direct involvement in teaching and supervising Home Economics instruction during the School Year 2025–2026.

Instruments

A structured questionnaire served as the primary data-gathering instrument. The questionnaire consisted of two parts. Part I measured the perceived level of learning competencies of Junior High School learners across four Home Economics strands: Dressmaking, Cookery, Handicraft Making, and Food Processing. Part II assessed the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by HE teachers that may affect learners' competencies. A Likert-scale format was used to quantify respondents' perceptions. The instrument was adapted from a validated questionnaire utilized in previous studies on Home Economics competencies of Junior High School learners.

Procedure

Approval to conduct the study was obtained from the Division Office of Manila City and the respective school principals. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires to the respondents, explained the purpose of the study, and ensured confidentiality and anonymity of responses. The retrieval rate of questionnaires was 100 percent.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, specifically the Average Weighted Mean, were used to determine the level of learning competencies and the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered. The t-test for

independent samples was employed to determine whether a significant difference existed between the perceptions of teachers and school heads at the 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

LEVEL OF LEARNING COMPETENCIES OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS IN DRESSMAKING AS PERCEIVED BY TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

The data in Table 2 indicate that the level of learning competencies of Junior High School learners in Dressmaking was generally rated as moderate. Teachers perceived learners' competencies with an overall mean of 3.13, while school heads rated them slightly higher at 3.28, resulting in an overall weighted mean of 3.21. Across the indicators, learners demonstrated consistent proficiency in performing basic hand sewing, operating sewing tools, applying finishing techniques, and observing safety practices, with the highest ratings given to observing safety practices (overall mean = 3.39). These results suggest that while learners show a moderate ability to perform dressmaking tasks, there is room for improvement in areas such as drafting patterns and constructing garments to meet quality standards. Overall, both teachers and school heads shared similar perceptions of learners' competencies, reflecting a consistent understanding of students' performance in the Dressmaking strand.

Table 2
Level of Learning Competencies of Junior High School Learners in Dressmaking
As Perceived by Teachers and School Heads

Indicators	Teachers		School Heads		Overall	
	Mean	DE	Mean	DE	Mean	DE
1. Interprets basic principles and elements of design	3.11	M	3.23	M	3.17	M
2. Performs basic hand sewing and stitches	3.15	M	3.35	M	3.25	M
3. Operates sewing tools and equipment	3.21	M	3.35	M	3.28	M
4. Drafts and cuts pattern based on body measurement	3.01	M	3.21	M	3.11	M
5. Constructs garment using appropriate techniques	3.05	M	3.26	M	3.16	M
6. Applies pressing and finishing techniques	3.12	M	3.24	M	3.18	M
7. Observes safety practices in dressmaking	3.34	M	3.43	M	3.39	M
8. Evaluates finished product based on quality standards	3.07	M	3.15	M	3.11	M
Total	3.13	M	3.28	M	3.21	M

LEVEL OF LEARNING COMPETENCIES OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS IN COOKERY AS PERCEIVED BY TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

The results in Table 3 show that the level of learning competencies of Junior High School learners in Cookery was generally rated as moderate. Teachers rated learners' overall competence at 3.30, while school heads gave a slightly lower rating of 3.26, resulting in an overall weighted mean of 3.28. Learners demonstrated consistent skills in using kitchen tools, preparing ingredients, following recipes, and applying proper safety and sanitation practices, with the highest competency observed in cooking dishes using various methods (overall mean = 3.30). The slightly lower scores in storing food products appropriately (overall mean = 3.18) indicate an area where learners may need additional guidance and practice. Overall, both teachers and school heads shared similar perceptions, reflecting a consistent understanding of learners' abilities in the Cookery strand.

Table 3
Level of Learning Competencies of Junior High School Learners in Cookery
As Perceived by Teachers and School Heads

Indicators	Teachers		School Heads		Overall	
	Mean	DE	Mean	DE	Mean	DE
1. Demonstrates proper kitchen safety and sanitation practices	3.31	M	3.30	M	3.31	M
2. Uses kitchen tools, equipment, and paraphernalia	3.33	M	3.34	M	3.34	M
3. Reads and interprets recipes	3.32	M	3.25	M	3.29	M
4. Prepares ingredients based on standard procedures	3.35	M	3.33	M	3.34	M
5. Cooks dishes using various cooking methods	3.36	M	3.23	M	3.30	M
6. Garnishes and presents cooked dishes creatively	3.29	M	3.28	M	3.29	M
7. Stores food products appropriately	3.23	M	3.12	M	3.18	M
8. Practices waste management and cost-effective techniques	3.24	M	3.23	M	3.24	M
Total	3.30	M	3.26	M	3.28	M

LEVEL OF LEARNING COMPETENCIES OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS IN HANDICRAFT MAKING AS PERCEIVED BY TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

The data in Table 4 indicate that the level of learning competencies of Junior High School learners in Handicraft Making was generally rated as moderate. Teachers perceived learners' competencies with an overall mean of 3.21, while school heads rated them slightly higher at 3.22, resulting in an overall weighted mean of 3.22. Learners showed consistent proficiency in identifying local resources, using tools properly, applying finishing techniques, and demonstrating creativity and entrepreneurship skills, with the highest ratings observed in creativity and innovation in design (overall mean = 3.31). The slightly lower score in practicing sustainability and eco-friendly methods (overall mean = 3.06) suggests a need for further reinforcement in this area. Overall, both teachers and school heads shared similar perceptions, indicating a consistent understanding of learners' abilities in the Handicraft Making strand.

Table 4
Level of Learning Competencies of Junior High School Learners in Handicraft Making As
Perceived by Teachers and School Heads

Indicators	Teachers		School Heads		Overall	
	Mean	DE	Mean	DE	Mean	DE
1. Identifies local resources for handicraft production	3.26	M	3.31	M	3.29	M
2. Demonstrates skills in basic handicraft production	3.19	M	3.20	M	3.20	M
3. Uses tools and equipment properly	3.28	M	3.33	M	3.31	M
4. Applies finishing techniques to products	3.19	M	3.21	M	3.20	M
5. Observes creativity and innovation in design	3.31	M	3.30	M	3.31	M
6. Demonstrates entrepreneurship skills in product selling	3.32	M	3.24	M	3.28	M
7. Practices sustainability and eco-friendly methods	3.00	M	3.11	M	3.06	M
8. Observes safety and health protocols	3.10	M	3.09	M	3.10	M
Total	3.21	M	3.22	M	3.22	M

LEVEL OF LEARNING COMPETENCIES OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS IN FOOD PROCESSING AS PERCEIVED BY TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

The results in Table 5 show that the level of learning competencies of Junior High School learners in Food Processing was generally rated as moderate. Teachers rated learners' overall competence at 3.22, while school heads gave a slightly lower rating of 3.20, resulting in an overall weighted mean of 3.21. Learners demonstrated consistent proficiency in identifying raw materials, preparing tools and equipment, and processing food according to standards, with the highest competency observed in identifying raw materials (overall mean = 3.33). Slightly lower scores were noted in demonstrating entrepreneurial skills in food marketing (overall mean = 3.03) and labeling and packaging processed food (overall mean = 3.08), indicating areas where learners may benefit from additional guidance and practice. Overall, both teachers and school heads shared similar perceptions, reflecting a consistent understanding of learners' abilities in the Food Processing strand.

Table 5
Level of Learning Competencies of Junior High School Learners in Food Processing As Perceived by Teachers and School Heads

Indicators	Teachers		School Heads		Overall	
	Mean	DE	Mean	DE	Mean	DE
1. Identifies raw materials for food processing	3.35	M	3.30	M	3.33	M
2. Prepares tools and equipment appropriately	3.29	M	3.32	M	3.31	M
3. Processes food based on standards and techniques	3.35	M	3.25	M	3.30	M
4. Practices hygiene and sanitation	3.25	M	3.23	M	3.24	M
5. Observes safety measures during processing	3.19	M	3.21	M	3.20	M
6. Labels and packages processed food	3.08	M	3.07	M	3.08	M
7. Stores processed food properly	3.23	M	3.21	M	3.22	M
8. Demonstrates entrepreneurial skills in food marketing	3.01	M	3.05	M	3.03	M
Total	3.22	M	3.20	M	3.21	M

SUMMARY OF THE LEVEL OF LEARNING COMPETENCIES OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS IN HOME ECONOMICS AS PERCEIVED BY TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

Table 6 presents a summary of the level of learning competencies of Junior High School learners in Home Economics as perceived by teachers and school heads. Overall, learners demonstrated moderate competency across all four strands. Teachers rated learners' competencies slightly lower (overall mean = 3.22) compared to school heads (overall mean = 3.24), resulting in an overall weighted mean of 3.23, interpreted as moderate. Among the strands, Cookery received the highest overall mean (3.28), suggesting relatively stronger performance in food preparation and related skills, while Dressmaking and Food Processing showed slightly lower but still moderate proficiency (3.21). Handicraft Making was also rated moderate (3.22), reflecting consistent but improvable skills in creativity, tool usage, and entrepreneurship. The results indicate that learners possess basic to developing competencies across all Home Economics strands, with areas for targeted improvement to further enhance practical and vocational skills.

Table 6
Summary of the Level of Learning Competencies of Junior High School Learners in Home Economics As Perceived by Teachers and School Heads

Home Economics Strands	Teachers		School Heads		Overall	
	Mean	DE	Mean	DE	AWM	DE
1. Dressmaking	3.13	M	3.28	M	3.21	M
2. Cookery	3.30	M	3.26	M	3.28	M
3. Handicraft Making	3.21	M	3.22	M	3.22	M
4. Food Processing	3.22	M	3.20	M	3.21	M
Total	3.22	M	3.24	M	3.23	M

SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCES IN THE LEVEL OF LEARNING COMPETENCIES OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS IN HOME ECONOMICS BETWEEN TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS

Table 7 shows the comparison of perceptions between teachers and school heads regarding the level of learning competencies of Junior High School learners in Home Economics. The overall average weighted mean for teachers was 3.22 and for school heads 3.24, both interpreted as moderate. The computed t-value of 0.6011, which is less than the critical value of 1.562 at the 0.05 level of significance, indicates that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and school heads. This suggests a shared understanding and consistent evaluation of learners' competencies across the four Home Economics strands: Dressmaking, Cookery, Handicraft Making, and Food Processing.

Table 7
Significant Differences in the Level of Learning Competencies of Junior High School Learners in Home Economics between Teachers and School Heads

Competence	Teachers		School Heads	
	AWM	DE	AWM	DE
1. Dressmaking	3.13	M	3.28	M
2. Cookery	3.30	M	3.26	M
3. Handicraft Making	3.21	M	3.22	M
4. Food Processing	3.22	M	3.20	M
Total	3.22	M	3.24	M

Computed t-value: 0.6011@ df 4
 Alpha: @ 0.05 level of significance
 Critical Value: 1.562, df 4
 Decision: accept the null hypothesis
 Interpretation: No significant difference

DEGREE OF SERIOUSNESS OF THE PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED BY TEACHERS

Table 8 presents the degree of seriousness of problems encountered by Home Economics teachers in developing the learning competencies of Junior High School learners. Overall, the problems were rated as moderately serious, with an overall mean of 2.26. Among the challenges, insufficient training or professional development opportunities for teachers was perceived as the most serious problem (mean = 2.42), followed closely by the lack of adequate teaching materials and equipment for practical lessons (mean = 2.39) and limited budget allocation for programs and activities (mean = 2.36). Other issues, such as limited time in the curriculum, lack of student interest, large class sizes, and difficulties aligning theory with practice, were also rated moderately serious, indicating that they pose notable but manageable obstacles to effective instruction. The findings highlight areas where support, resources, and professional development are needed to strengthen the implementation of practical and competency-based Home Economics education.

Table 8
Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered

Indicators	Teachers		Rank
	Mean	DE	
1. Lack of adequate teaching materials and equipment for Home Economics practical lessons	2.39	S	3
2. Insufficient training or professional development opportunities for teachers	2.42	S	1
3. Limited time allocated to Home Economics subjects in the school curriculum	2.30	MS	6
4. Lack of student interest or motivation in Home Economics subjects	2.24	MS	8
5. Limited budget allocation for Home Economics programs and activities	2.36	S	4
6. Large class sizes hindering effective practical demonstrations and individualized instruction	2.12	MS	9
7. Difficulty in aligning theoretical knowledge with practical Learning Competencies development	2.25	MS	7
8. Challenges in keeping up-to-date with the latest industry standards	2.01	MS	10
9. Poor student attendance affecting consistent Learning Competencies development	1.98	MS	11
10. Limited access to community or industry partnerships for experiential learning opportunities	2.32	MS	5
Total	2.26	MS	

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the level of learning competencies of Junior High School learners in Home Economics in District V, Manila City Division, is generally moderate

across the four strands—Dressmaking, Cookery, Handicraft Making, and Food Processing—as perceived by both teachers and school heads. This indicates that while learners have acquired foundational practical skills, there is still room for further development to achieve higher proficiency. The study also revealed that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and school heads regarding learners' competencies, suggesting a shared understanding and consistent assessment of students' abilities across the Home Economics strands. Furthermore, the problems encountered by teachers in developing these competencies were rated as moderately serious, with insufficient professional development, lack of teaching materials and equipment, and limited budget for programs identified as the most pressing challenges. These findings underscore the need for an action plan to address these issues and enhance learners' competencies through targeted interventions, including teacher training, provision of instructional resources, improved facilities, and strategies to increase student engagement and motivation in practical Home Economics lessons.

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